

The Impact of Emotional Artificial Intelligence

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Introduction and research description

In the field of artificial intelligence, efforts to design tools that can understand and manage interactions with humans by taking emotions into account have sparked significant debate. Over the past few years, this issue has increasingly featured in public discussions, with numerous articles, reports, and opinion pieces appearing in the press. The study conducted at the University of Rennes aims to capture the contours of this public debate on emotional AI. It seeks to identify the perceived benefits and the value these innovations promise, while also highlighting the risks and potential threats they may entail.

Our study is based on an analysis of 43 press articles published in 2024 and 2025. These articles were identified using keyword searches in specialized databases. For each article, we produced a summary identifying the type of piece, the actors mentioned, and the arguments put forward, whether they emphasized positive or negative values associated with emotional artificial intelligence. We then compared these arguments in order to extract the main themes and positions.

In this article, we present three key issues raised in the public debate on emotional AI, focusing on perceived affective and social risks. Our aim is to analyze these concerns in order to guide the development of this technology towards a greater consideration of the fears expressed in societal debate.

Risks of Emotional Manipulation

Public debate on emotional AI highlights a central concern: the risk of emotional manipulation built on the simulation of relational closeness that exploits human vulnerabilities. Designed to mimic empathy and create the illusion of an authentic bond, these systems can trigger strong attachment, particularly among individuals who are isolated or in distress. Several experts stress that such tools, often marketed as “companions,” are in fact commercial services disguised behind an emotional façade. This confusion can foster therapeutic expectations that AI cannot fulfill, thereby heightening the risk of emotional dependence and psychological harm.

The mechanisms of this manipulation rely on anthropomorphism and the use of linguistic cues designed to reinforce user identification. By constructing artificial “personalities,” companies amplify the illusion of relationship and encourage potentially addictive behaviors. Even seemingly trivial exchanges, such as being polite to a chatbot, contribute to normalizing an artificial bond.

In some cases, AI responses are perceived as more empathetic than those of humans, shifting trust toward systems that have no real sensitivity. This strategy reflects a broader logic of commercial exploitation of emotion, where “empathy at scale” is primarily used to capture attention and harvest sensitive data, turning human feelings into marketable resources.

Risks of Emotional Dependence

Similarly, debates on emotional AI emphasize the dangers of emotional dependence it can generate. Marketed as ever-available interlocutors, “empathetic” chatbots appear to offer support in situations of loneliness or limited psychological resources. Yet several investigations show that this simulated closeness can foster excessive attachment, particularly among vulnerable individuals.

A study reported by France 24 revealed that some emotionally distressed users begin to expect genuine therapeutic advice from these systems, even though they lack both subjectivity and clinical competence. As psychiatrist Serge Tisseron warns, “these systems make us believe they understand us, but they feel nothing,” exposing individuals to the risk of confusing technical interaction with human relationship.

This shift fuels concerns about a form of false psychological support, where the unlimited availability of these tools creates an illusion of care that may prevent people from seeking human assistance. Clinicians underline that AI cannot provide transfer, lived temporality, or true relational depth, and that its “empathy” is merely a formal simulation.

As Le Figaro/madame Figaro notes, “AI is not our friend; it tells us what we want to hear,” which may worsen distress rather than alleviate it. Troubling cases, particularly involving minors, have shown that AI responses can sometimes be inappropriate or even harmful. In this light, the press evokes the prospect of a public health crisis, with dependence on virtual companions comparable to social media addiction, exacerbated by the temptation to use these technologies as substitutes for real therapeutic support.

Risks of Dehumanization

The third major risk identified in our press analysis concerns the progressive dehumanization linked to the growing use of emotional AI in social interactions. Researchers cited by Le Monde stress that the normalization of artificial conversations is reshaping traditional social norms: politeness, intimacy, and the search for comfort are increasingly transferred to machines.

This substitution undermines the value of human exchanges, particularly in educational and family settings, where learning about otherness and emotions depends on relationships with others. Several psychologists warn of the cumulative effect of this trend, noting that by delegating emotional reassurance to artificial systems, we diminish the essential role of human interaction in the construction of social bonds.

This concern is compounded by the problem of cognitive saturation, induced by systems deliberately designed to hold users' attention and prolong interactions. As highlighted in the Cash Investigation report, these digital companions employ systematic prompting mechanisms that make it difficult to disengage, fostering a distracting form of dependence. Such constant overstimulation weakens concentration and erodes critical autonomy, an especially pressing issue among younger generations. Ultimately, the convergence of these dynamics, relational substitution and cognitive capture, fuels the fear of a lasting weakening of human connection and an impoverishment of social life.

Toward Human-Centered Emotional AI

Our analysis of the public debate on emotional AI highlights risks that affect both individuals and society as a whole. Whether these risks are already evident or only anticipated, they demand careful attention. The development of emotional artificial intelligence must be grounded in full respect for people's fundamental interests, their dignity, and their autonomy. Above all, it should serve a vision of human empowerment, ensuring that technology remains a tool for support rather than an instrument of manipulation or dependence.

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